

Role of Farmer Producer companies with help of farmers availability of new market in India for their commodity

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Abstract:

The size of operational holdings in India is continuously declining with every successive generation. The situation has raised serious question on the survivability of these small holders. On the other hand, the rapid increase in population coupled with substantive increase in incomes and purchasing power has led to increased demand for quality food and agricultural products. Being smallholders, these farmers suffer from some inherent problems such as absence of economies of scale, access to information and their inability to participate in the price discovery mechanism. The participation of farmers is observed to be restricted by limitations like poor vertical and horizontal linkages and limited access to market, training and to finance. Poor information flow along the chain, has also been identified as a vital constraint. The problem of access to market is even more pronounced for small and marginal farmers

Introduction

Farmer Producer Organisation (FPO) is a generic name, which refers to farmer-producers' organization incorporated/ registered either under Part IXA of Companies Act or under Co-operative Societies Act of the concerned States and formed for the purpose of leveraging collectives through economies of scale in production and marketing of agricultural and allied sector. The concept behind Farmer Producer Organizations is that farmers, who are the producers of agricultural products, can form groups. To facilitate this process, the Small Farmers' Agribusiness Consortium (SFAC) was mandated by Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Govt. of India, to support the State Governments in the formation of Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs). The Government of India has approved and launched a Central Sector Scheme of "Formation and Promotion of 10,000 Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs)" to form and promote 10,000 new FPOs till 2027-28. Prime Minister Narendra Modi, on 29 February 2020[5], launched 10,000 FPOs across India from Chitrakoot. Under the scheme, the formation and promotion of FPO is based on Produce Cluster Area approach and specialized commodity-based approach. While adopting cluster-based approach, formation of FPOs will be focussed on "One District One Product" for development of product specialization. Nearly 86 per cent of farmers are small and marginal with average land holdings in the country being less than 1.1 hectare. These small, marginal and landless farmers face tremendous challenges during agriculture production phase such as for access to

technology, quality seed, fertilizers and pesticides including requisite finances. They also face tremendous challenges in marketing their produce due to lack of economic strength. FPOs help in collectivization of such small, marginal and landless farmers in order to give them the collective strength to deal with such issues. Members of the FPO will manage their activities together in the organization to get better access to technology, input, finance and market for faster enhancement of their income.

Research Methodology

To understand the current trends and patterns in FPOs, we analysed the data on FPO supported by National Bank for Rural Development (NABARD) and Small Farmers Producer Organization (SFAC). NABARD and SFAC under various programmes support FPOs and maintain a database on their name, location, commodity and business activity in their sites (provide the sites; NABARD- <https://nabfpo.in/images/staticFPO.html>, SFAC - <http://sfacindia.com/List-of-FPO-Statewise.aspx>). The state level distribution of the number of FPOs and their legal status were tabulated and visualized in GIS graphs. The commodity and business activities of FPOs were captured using word cloud. Word cloud is an image composed of words and size of each word indicates the frequency of the word. Visualization of commodity and business activity provide insights major commodity and business activity among the FPOs.

Objective:

1. To Study the role of farmer producer companies for solving problems of new market for availability in India

2. To Study the various issues and Challenges in farmer producer companies to growth and market facility for farmers in India.
3. To Study the development farmer producer companies marketing for farmer's commodity in agriculture sector in India
4. To Study conclusion and measure of marketing facility for farmers for farmer producer companies in India

To Study the role of farmer producer companies for solving problems of new market for availability in India

The growth in the Indian agriculture sector has been impressive in the last three decades except for a few years of ups and downs. There is an increase in production of all agriculture and allied products over a period of time. Even during the Pandemic situation, the growth in the agriculture sector was positive. However, over a period of time, it is observed that the per capita income of the farmers has been lowest among all the sectors. The major constraint of Indian agriculture is the diminishing size of landholding. As per the 2015 census, the proportion of small and marginal farmers is more than 85 percent of total land holdings in the agricultural economy of India. Being smallholders, these farmers suffer from some inherent problems such as the absence of economies of scale, access to information, and their inability to participate in the price discovery mechanism. The only way to solve the problems of these small holders is to aggregate them into a group so that there will be operation of economics of scale. Thus, given the situation of the smallholders, their problems are of prime concern for the sector. Various institutional interventions by government, private and civil society organizations, have tried to link smallholders to the input and/or output markets.

To Study the various issues and Challenges in farmer producer companies to growth and market facility for farmers in India.

Various institutional interventions started by government, private and civil society organizations, have tried to link smallholders to the input and/or output markets. Several attempts have been made to aggregate the farmers into different forms of groups. However, the success achieved has been limited. These include agricultural cooperatives, self-help groups, commodity interest groups, farmer producer organizations, producer companies, etc. There is a need for aggregation of farmers in order to benefit from economies of scale. Group members are able to leverage collective strength and bargaining power to access inputs,

services and appropriate technologies leading to reduction in transaction costs. Recently, a new model of aggregation in the form of Farmer Producer Company (FPC) has evolved. The instrument of Farmer Producer Company (FPC), registered under Companies Act, 1956 is emerging as an effective Farmer Producer Organization (FPO) to cater to the aggregation needs of farmers at the grass root level. The main objective of mobilizing farmers into member-owned producer companies, or FPCs, is to enhance production, productivity and profitability of agriculturists, especially small farmers in the country. It takes care of the entire supply chain and hence is a distinguished model compared to other aggregation models. FPCs offer a wide range of benefits compared to other formats of aggregation of the farmers. Its main activities consist of production, harvesting, processing, procurement, grading, pooling, handling, marketing, selling, and export of primary produce of the members or import of goods or services for their benefit. It provides for sharing of profits/benefits among the members. This issue of the Extension Digest focuses on the rationale for Farmer Producer Organization/Companies; concept and genesis of FPOs/FPCs; policy issues for promotion of FPOs/FPCs and presents some Success stories of these Organizations. I am glad to inform that "Extension Digest" is revived after a gap of 16 years with a timely theme on "Harnessing Social Media for Agricultural Development". Social Media have now become an important means of communication for everyone in all the sectors. These tools are impacting the agriculture sector too. Social Media applications are providing new opportunities for Agricultural Research, Extension, Education and Marketing Organisations to communicate and collaborate and enabling exchange of information and networking among agricultural officers and farmers. More importantly, Social Media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Blogs, Twitter, What Sapp, YouTube, Skype etc., are not only enabling scientists and extension professionals share information but also empowering farmers to link to markets and consumers for better profits. Social Media also provide opportunity to farmers to share their farm practices, challenges and the great service they are doing in order to feed the population. There is a need to harness Social Media for agricultural development by all actors especially the agricultural extension professionals who play a major role in disseminating technologies and innovations to farmers. It is necessary to equip extension personnel on Social Media concepts, applications and

communication strategies in order to harness Social Media for effective sharing of agricultural information. This issue of the Extension Digest focuses on Social media and application in agriculture and allied sectors and also shares cases which demonstrate the power of Social Media in effective sharing of agricultural information and knowledge and networking. I am sure that this Extension Digest issue w

To Study the development farmer producer companies marketing for farmer's commodity in agriculture sector in India

The crux of the problems faced by small and marginal farmers may be traced to limited bargaining power and inability to benefit from economies of scale when compared to large farmers. Of several strategies developed and various methods tried across the world, group approach has proved to be effective in boosting up their bargaining power and scaling up the production process and in doing so can reap numerous benefits as compared to individual approach. Due to factors beyond their control and absence of institutions to safeguard their interests, they are unable to integrate with the agricultural value chains, fight the risks and vulnerabilities such as commodity price volatility, crop failure, insect pest-attacks etc. on their own. Therefore, they are operating at sub-optimal level and thus attain lower equilibrium. Collectivizing farmers, thus, into Producer Organizations (POs) has been considered as one of the ways to overcome these challenges faced by the small and marginal farmers. The approach is considered to be helpful in integrating the farmers directly, through their institutions (producer companies/ cooperatives), to market, for both, inputs and output, collective processing and marketing whereas production is largely left to the individual small farms. This interest is primarily based on the premise that FPOs give small farmers bargaining power in the market place, enable cost-effective delivery of extension services, and empower the members to influence the policies that affect their livelihoods. Integrating small farmer producers, however, is a challenge due to several factors like, (i) small farmers are not a homogenous group and majority of them lack entrepreneurial faculty. (ii) Dispersed locations posing problems in logistics like, packaging, storing and aggregation and also in organizing them into collectives, (iii) production in small quantity and absence of primary processing and value addition weakens their bargaining power, (IV) non-existence of price discovery mechanism due to problems in access to market information, market inefficiencies.

However, several initiatives have been taken by the Government of India (GoI) for collectivizing farmers into FPOs. Small Farmers' Agri Business Consortium (SFAC), was mandated by the GoI to support formation of FPOs. NABARD as the apex financial institutions for financing agriculture created its own window as Producers Organization Development Fund (PODF) in 2011 for financing FPOs.

To Study conclusion and measure of marketing facility for farmers for farmer producer companies in India

The agricultural marketing plays a vital role in easy way agro produce distribution to the customers. Like all the marketing activities, it also aims in profit making. It helps the farmers to reach their customers within very short lead time, Small and marginal farmers in India have been vulnerable to risks in agricultural production. Several organizational prototypes are emerging to integrate them into the value chain with the objective of enhancing incomes and reducing transaction costs. Among these are Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs). We explore the potential of FPOs as collective institutions through a case study of Avirat, one of the first FPOs in Gujarat. Our analysis suggests that FPOs have the potential to provide benefits through effective collective action. The main challenge, however, is to raise sufficient capital to maximize these benefits. We discuss the implications of our findings to policy. A village makes no progress if its farmers are not modern. If the way of farming remains what it always was, nobody earns much money. The young people won't stay in the village, because they want to earn more money to satisfy all their new needs

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